

Developing Professionally Relevant Skills in Philology Students Through the Analysis of Modern Texts

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Abstract: The article explores approaches to developing professionally relevant skills in philology students through the analysis of modern texts. It describes the key competencies required for future philologists, such as critical thinking, interpretative skills, and the ability to work with texts of various genres. Special attention is given to methods of analyzing media, literary, and online texts as tools for fostering analytical thinking, linguistic competence, and professional preparedness among students.

Keywords: critical thinking, modern texts, philology students, text analysis, linguistic competence, interpretative skills, digital communication, media texts, stylistic analysis, cultural context

Introduction

Modern philology is evolving in the context of a rapidly changing informational landscape, where texts acquire new forms and functions. Future philologists face the challenge of working with texts that go beyond traditional literary genres. These texts may include not only artistic works but also media articles, advertisements, and online discourse that blend elements of visual, oral, and written communication. Analyzing such texts requires a high level of linguistic, cultural, and technological competence. Integrating the study of modern texts into the educational process not only prepares students for new professional challenges but also helps them develop a profound understanding of language as a dynamic system.

1. The Importance of Modern Texts in Philological Education

Modern texts reflect changes in society, culture, and language. For instance, the use of anglicisms, emojis, and internet slang in social networks demonstrates how globalization influences linguistic systems. These elements, despite their apparent simplicity, carry deep cultural and social information. Analyzing such texts helps students understand how language adapts to new realities and how it shapes the perception of information.

Additionally, modern texts offer a unique opportunity to study cultural codes and their transformations. Advertising slogans such as *"Live bright!"* or *"Be yourself"* reflect the values of individualism and freedom characteristic of contemporary culture. Including such examples in the educational process allows students to understand how language is used to create a specific emotional and social message and to study its impact on the audience.

2. Developing Key Professional Skills

Working with modern texts promotes the development of several professional skills essential in the context of a changing linguistic landscape.

- **Critical Thinking:** This skill helps students analyze texts, identify manipulative strategies, and recognize rhetorical techniques used to influence audiences. For example, dissecting headlines like *"You won't believe what happened..."* can help students uncover elements of emotional manipulation.
- **Interpretative Skills:** Students learn to understand subtext, allusions, and metaphors, which is particularly important when working with artistic texts. For instance, examining modern memes enriched with cultural references reveals how language becomes a tool for collective creativity and cultural identification.
- **Editorial and Stylistic Skills:** Modern texts often exhibit hybrid styles. Working with such texts enables students to learn how to edit and adapt texts for different target audiences, a critical skill for professional success.

3. Methodological Approaches to Analyzing Modern Texts

Educators can employ various methodological approaches to help students master the skills of text analysis and interpretation.

- **Analyzing Media Texts:** Students can work with news articles, identifying manipulative elements and rhetorical techniques. For instance, examining the tone and structure of news headlines helps understand how the media shapes public opinion.
- **Working with Online Texts:** Analyzing comments, posts, and memes on social media develops students' ability to recognize cultural codes, interpret visual and textual elements, and understand the specifics of digital communication.
- **Comparative Analysis:** Comparing modern literary works with classical texts allows students to identify changes in language, style, and content. For example, studying the works of contemporary authors alongside 19th-century prose reveals the evolution of literary traditions and techniques.

4. Challenges and Prospects of Analyzing Modern Texts

Modern texts often feature hybrid characteristics, combining visual, textual, and auditory elements, which complicates their analysis. For example, advertising texts or slogans may simultaneously appeal to sight, hearing, and emotional perception. This requires students to consider the context and specific features of such texts during analysis.

The prospects of analyzing modern texts are linked to the use of digital technologies. Analyzing large data sets, such as social media comments or search queries, allows for the identification of new lexical and grammatical trends and their impact on language. This opens new opportunities for students to deepen their knowledge of modern language dynamics.

Conclusion

Engaging with modern texts is an integral part of training philology students. It helps them develop critical thinking, interpretative skills, and stylistic analysis capabilities, equipping them to work in a constantly evolving linguistic environment. Incorporating modern texts into the educational process contributes not only to students' professional training but also to their cultural development, enabling them to gain a deeper understanding of the specific features of contemporary language and culture.

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